

WOMEN IN URBAN INFORMAL ECONOMY: CASE STUDY OF DOMESTIC WORKERS AND STREET VENDORS IN GURUGRAM

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Article Info

Received on: 22 Apr 2025

Accepted on: 26 Aug 2025

Available online: 10-Sep-2025

Cite This Article As

Samaya C & Faraz A (2025), “women in urban informal economy: case study of domestic workers and street vendors in Gurugram”, International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, Volume 12, Issue 1, 2025, pp 52-71. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17959274>

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the socio-economic conditions of women informal workers in Gurugram, focusing on domestic workers and street vendors through a mixed-methods case study. The findings reveal that most women are migrants with low education, earning minimal and irregular wages while working long hours without contracts or social protection. Challenges include wage disparity, unsafe conditions, harassment, and limited access to welfare schemes. Despite their crucial contribution to urban households and markets, women's informal labour remains undervalued and vulnerable. The study calls for targeted policy interventions to ensure legal recognition, social security, gender-sensitive labour protections, and improved economic opportunities.

Keywords: Women Workers, Informal Sector, Gender Inequality

1. INTRODUCTION:

The informal economy forms the backbone of India's labour market, employing nearly 90 percent of the workforce and contributing substantially to the nation's economic growth (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). Unlike formal employment, work in the informal sector is characterized by the absence of contracts, social security benefits, stable wages, and legal protections (ILO, 2018). Despite its centrality to India's economic structure, the informal economy remains marginalized in policy discourse, and the contributions of its workers are systematically

undervalued. Women, in particular, occupy a disproportionately large share of informal employment, where they often face precarious conditions, low wages, and lack of recognition.

Within the urban informal economy, women are concentrated in occupations such as domestic work and street vending. Domestic workers, engaged in household tasks like cooking, cleaning, and childcare, provide indispensable services for middle- and upper-class households but remain invisible in labour legislation and protection mechanisms. Street vendors, on the other hand, sustain urban food supply chains and retail networks yet often face harassment from authorities, insecure livelihoods, and exclusion from social security. Together, these occupations reflect the dual dynamics of women's labour in both private spaces (households) and public spaces (markets and streets), underscoring the pervasive gendered vulnerabilities of informal employment.

The increasing participation of women in urban informal work is shaped by multiple structural drivers, including poverty, migration, lack of education, and restrictive gender norms. Migrant women, in particular, enter informal occupations due to their limited access to social networks and formal sector opportunities in cities. At the same time, women's work in these sectors is systematically devalued—seen as an extension of domestic responsibilities rather than recognized as skilled economic activity. This invisibility not only contributes to gender wage gaps but also perpetuates women's socio-economic marginalization.

Despite the scale of women's involvement in urban informal work, research and policy frameworks remain inadequate in addressing their specific challenges. Studies have highlighted issues such as *wage disparity*, *job insecurity*, *lack of maternity benefits*, *harassment*, and *unsafe working conditions* (NCEUS, 2007; WIEGO, 2018). However, much of this research is aggregated at the national level and *fails to capture the lived realities of women in specific occupations and urban contexts*. There is, therefore, a pressing need to examine women's experiences in the informal urban economy through *focused case studies* that highlight both their *vulnerabilities* and their agency

The informal sector includes all types of work that are not officially registered or supervised by the government. Unlike formal jobs, these forms of employment usually lack written agreements, steady income, or benefits such as health insurance, pensions, and paid leave (Bordoloi, Pandey, & Farooqui, 2020). Common examples of such work are domestic services, small-scale farming, street vending, construction labour, and home-based activities like tailoring or handicrafts.

Figure 1: Gender wise Share of Informal Workers in Different Sectors

Source: Compiled by the Author from Government of India (2024). Labor Bureau of India. STATISTA

Even though it operates outside formal systems, the informal sector plays a vital role in India’s economy by providing jobs to a large section of the population. Women make up a major share of this unorganized workforce. Factors such as poverty, limited education, social barriers, and the need to balance family duties with earning a living often push women into informal employment. These jobs are easier to access and more flexible, but they usually come with very low wages, no legal protection, and unsafe working conditions. From villages to cities, women contribute significantly as farm workers, vendors, domestic helpers, and home-based producers, yet much of their labour goes unnoticed and undervalued.

This paper aims to study the situation of women in India’s informal sector. It will look at the kind of work they do, the difficulties they face, and their contribution to the economy. Finally, it will discuss ways in which their rights can be protected and their role given greater recognition, so that women workers can move towards empowerment and equality.

1.1 Role of Women in Informal Sector:

Women in India play an indispensable role in the country’s workforce, particularly in the informal sector, yet their contributions frequently go unrecognized or undervalued.

Figure 2: Percentage of Males & Females engaged in the Informal Sector in India

Source: compiled by the Author from ILOSTAT (2023). Informal Employment rate by Sex Percentage: ILO

Recent data show that among females aged 15 and above, the overall labour force participation rate (LFPR) in 2023-24 was 32.8% nationwide, with rural areas notably higher at 36.6% compared to 23.8% in urban locations. In rural India, about 73% of working women are involved in agriculture, handling critical tasks such as sowing seeds, weeding fields, harvesting crops, and tending live stock jobs that contribute directly to both household and national food security. Despite this majority involvement, only 14% of agricultural land holdings are in women's names, highlighting systemic barriers to property ownership and capital for women.

Apart from agriculture, rural women earn incomes through home-based occupations like rolling beedis, weaving textiles, embroidery, and preparing papads in industries where earnings may be modest but are vital for family support. In urban areas, the share of women in the workforce is lower, yet almost 97.7% of urban female workers are employed in informal or unorganized segments, such as domestic work, street vending, small-scale garment production, and construction labour. Many urban women serve as domestic workers, taking on roles like cooking, cleaning, and childcare, while others work as daily-wage labourers at construction sites or as vendors in local markets.

This pervasive dominance of women in the informal sector is also reflected in government and independent studies: from 2017-18 to 2023-24, India's female workforce participation rate almost doubled, reaching 40.3% yet much of this rise is attributed to casual, self-employment, or unprotected jobs with little social security or benefits. The Worker Population Ratio (WPR) for rural women stood at 33.6% in June 2025, while for urban women, it was 22.9%; both figures are far below men's participation rates.

Globally, India ranks among the lowest in female labor force participation, trailing other G20 countries and its regional neighbors, with current rates at least 20 percentage points lower than the G20 average of ~50%. This gap highlights both the scale of women's contribution and the persistent marginalization and undervaluation of their work—often described as “helping the family” rather than acknowledged as a significant economic force. The facts and statistics underline the indispensable nature of women's labor within every segment of the informal economy, and emphasize the urgent need for recognition and empowerment policies moving forward.

In India, a large proportion of women are engaged in the informal sector, and this is the result of multiple social and economic factors. Poverty is the leading reason, with about 35 percent of women workers forced to accept irregular, insecure, and poorly paid jobs in order to contribute to household survival. Another major factor is the absence of education and skill training, which explains nearly 25 percent of women's dependence on informal employment. In many rural areas, girls leave school early due to financial difficulties or social customs, which prevents them from qualifying for steady work in the organized sector.

Table-1: Groups of workers by highest level of education and sex in India, Urban India (2017-18) in Percentage

Worker Category	Education Level	India – Total	India – Women	India – Men	Urban – Total	Urban – Women	Urban – Men
Home-Based Workers	Below Primary	30.6	41.3	23.1	24.0	32.7	18.2
	Primary to Middle	37.4	35.3	38.8	35.1	36.1	34.4
	Secondary & Higher	22.2	17.2	25.6	25.9	21.4	28.8
	Graduate & Above	9.8	6.1	12.4	15.0	9.7	18.6
Domestic Workers	Below Primary	50.9	61.1	32.1	54.9	60.6	38.7
	Primary to Middle	37.1	33.1	44.7	34.6	33.7	37.1
	Secondary & Higher	10.0	5.1	18.9	8.7	5.0	19.5
	Graduate & Above	2.0	0.7	4.3	1.8	0.8	4.6
Street Vendors / Traders	Below Primary	32.2	63.0	28.7	30.0	64.6	25.7
	Primary to Middle	38.5	24.9	40.1	38.8	22.3	40.8
	Secondary & Higher	22.7	9.4	24.2	23.3	10.9	24.9
	Graduate & Above	6.5	2.7	7.0	7.9	2.2	8.6
Waste Pickers	Below Primary	44.6	63.6	35.3	48.6	66.5	39.1
	Primary to Middle	39.2	26.3	45.5	38.9	28.7	44.3
	Secondary & Higher	14.0	9.4	16.3	11.1	4.8	14.4
	Graduate & Above	2.3	0.7	3.0	1.4	0.0	2.2
Construction Workers	Below Primary	36.7	65.1	33.5	34.5	62.6	31.9
	Primary to Middle	43.7	27.2	45.5	42.3	28.8	44.3
	Secondary & Higher	17.3	6.3	18.5	18.7	4.8	14.4
	Graduate & Above	2.3	1.4	4.6	4.6	3.7	2.2
Transport Workers	Below Primary	20.1	9.6	20.2	18.5	15.0	18.5

	Primary to Middle	46.0	7.0	46.2	45.7	10.2	45.9
	Secondary & Higher	29.3	36.7	29.3	29.6	52.1	29.5
	Graduate & Above	4.5	46.7	4.3	6.2	22.7	6.1

Source: WIEGO. (2020). *Informal Workers in India: A Statistical Profile*, 14-15

The data shows that informal workers in India and urban India are predominantly concentrated in the lower education brackets, especially among women. For categories like domestic workers, waste pickers, and construction workers, more than half of women have education below the primary level.

Migration also plays a significant role, as around 15 percent of women who move with their families from villages to towns end up in casual daily-wage jobs because they lack connections and resources to find formal employment. Social and cultural norms add further restrictions, pushing another 15 percent of women into informal occupations such as domestic service or home-based activities, which are flexible but unstable. Gender inequality also remains a key barrier, directly affecting about 10 percent of women through unequal wages and employers' reluctance to provide maternity benefits or legal protections. All of these pressures combine to keep women concentrated in insecure, low-paying jobs, leaving them vulnerable to exploitation and economic hardship.

1.2 Challenges for Women in Informal Sector:

Employment for women in India is overwhelmingly informal – **about 90% of all workers are informal, and 92% of women lack formal jobs** (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). This means most working **women have no legal contracts, social security or benefits**. Recent surveys and reports highlight five key problems faced by these women: Women in informal jobs earn far less than men. For example, an ILO analysis of NSSO data found that by 2011–12 women's average pay was about 34% lower than men's (down from 48% in 1993–94) (ILO, 2018). In practice, women's wages often fall below the legal minimum. A WIEGO study (2017–18) shows that all examined groups of female workers earn under the recommended ₹46.88/hour (₹375/day) minimum (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020).

Table 2: Average hourly earnings of groups of workers by sex, urban India

Worker Category	Group	India	Urban India
Home-Based Workers	All	39.75	48.73
	Women	23.93	29.34
	Men	48.24	59.06
Domestic Workers	All	28.71	28.56
	Women	24.56	25.17
	Men	36.33	38.26
Street Vendors & Traders	All	38.87	41.39

	Women	29.07	31.52
	Men	39.68	42.32
Waste Pickers	All	38.53	39.46
	Women	30.41	30.86
	Men	42.46	44.11
Construction Workers	All	38.89	45.45
	Women	26.15	30.97
	Men	39.95	46.60
Transport Workers	All	42.94	47.35
	Women	45.99	45.39
	Men	42.93	47.36

Source: WIEGO. (2020). Informal Workers in India: A Statistical Profile, 9-10

Specific figures illustrate this gap: home-based women averaged only ₹23.93/hour (all India) versus ₹48.24/hour for men. Similarly, female domestic helpers earned about ₹24.56/hour vs ₹36.33 for men. In home-based industries nationwide, one estimate reports 17.19 million women earn ~₹24/hour on average (half the male rate ~₹48/hr). Even in high-earning urban groups (e.g. informal transport), women's pay (~₹45.39/hr) just barely reaches the minimum wage (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). In rural areas the gap can be wider – for low-education workers, rural women earned only about 53% of male wages. In short, women's incomes are low and very irregular (often paid by the hour or by piece work), which keeps them in poverty.

Informal jobs offer almost no security. Most women are on daily-wage or self-employment arrangements, not on paid leave or contracts. For example, in informal construction almost 98% of women are classified as casual workers (paid daily, no guaranteed work) compared to 85% of men. In many sectors women are self-employed or “home-based”, meaning work can end overnight. Even in domestic work (which is called “regular employment” in surveys), these are unregulated home jobs. Nationally 90% of female domestic helpers are labelled “regular employees” vs 79% of men, but this still lacks any legal tenure or benefits. In informal transport, women are somewhat more likely to be ‘regular’ (85% of women vs 36% of men) but “regular” here still means no formal contract. In short, virtually no women in the informal sector have stable contracts; they can be let go with no notice or compensation.

Because informal women lack formal employment, almost none get paid maternity leave or health coverage. Under India's Maternity Benefit Act, only formal-sector employees are eligible, and small employers are exempt. In practice, a recent analysis of labour data shows 93.5% of working women (mostly informal) cannot access paid maternity leave at all. Similarly, access to health insurance is very low: NFHS-5 (2020–21) found only about 30% of women aged 15–49 had any health insurance or scheme (33% of men). Without insurance or paid leave, new mothers in the informal sector must either stop working (with no income)

or return to work almost immediately. A survey notes many women continue heavy work late into pregnancy because they have no alternative, risking their health and that of their baby.

Beyond lower pay, informal women face systemic bias. Employers often assign them the lowest-paying tasks. Even the figures above show *unequal pay for equal work*. The raw pay gap (~34%) is a form of discrimination. Moreover, women in the informal sector rarely benefit from labour laws or unions. For example, India's Workplace Sexual Harassment (POSH) law applies to "workplaces" that informal women often don't fall under. Observers note that this law has largely *failed* to protect marginalized informal women, meaning cases of abuse or harassment on construction sites or in homes generally go unaddressed. In the absence of formal grievance mechanisms, many women endure verbal abuse, wage theft or sexual harassment with impunity.

Many informal jobs expose women to serious health risks. In agriculture, women laborers spend long hours bent over fields, carrying heavy loads, and handling pesticides. A government commission (NCEUS) found very high rates of illness among rural women: chronic back pain, respiratory problems (from dust and crops), skin conditions (from chemicals), and general fatigue were common. In construction, around 93% of workers are informal. Female construction workers (often migrants) typically have *no* safety gear or training, work at height or with heavy materials, and lack basic services. Reports highlight that many women work without toilets or clean water, suffer malnutrition and anemia, and even work into late pregnancy with no maternity support. Home-based and cottage work (weaving, garment stitching, agarbatti rolling, etc.) often involve cramped, unventilated spaces and exposure to dust, smoke or toxins from glues and dyes – but these hazards are rarely documented or mitigated. Domestic workers labor in private homes for long hours (often 12+ hours/day) with minimal breaks; they handle cleaning chemicals, biomass cooking smoke, and carry young children, all without any labor oversight. In summary, informal women face unsafe, unhealthy conditions with no occupational health measures in place.

1.3 Statement of the problem

Despite accounting for nearly 90 percent of India's workforce, the informal sector remains undervalued and underrepresented in policy frameworks. Women form a disproportionately large share of this workforce, particularly in urban contexts, where they are concentrated in precarious occupations such as domestic work and street vending. ***These women face multiple intersecting challenges: they earn significantly lower wages than men, often below statutory minimum levels; lack employment contracts and social security benefits; and work in unsafe, exploitative conditions.*** Their labor is frequently devalued, treated as supplementary rather than recognized as skilled economic contribution, reinforcing gender discrimination and socio-economic marginalization.

Moreover, existing research tends to aggregate women's informal work at the national level, thereby overlooking the nuanced experiences of specific occupational groups and urban contexts. This invisibility contributes to a gap between policy intentions and the lived

realities of women workers. Without focused, occupation-specific studies, the structural drivers of informality—poverty, migration, limited education, and restrictive gender norms—remain inadequately addressed. The present study seeks to fill this gap by foregrounding the experiences of domestic workers and street vendors in urban areas of Gurugram, highlighting both their vulnerabilities and their strategies of resilience.

1.4 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the research study are as follows:

- 1) To analyze the socio-demographic and economic profile of women in domestic work and street vending in Gurugram.
- 2) To identify the major challenges faced by women informal workers, including wage disparity.
- 3) To analyse gender based inequalities.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The informal economy has emerged as the largest source of employment for women in India, where nearly 90 percent of the female workforce operates outside formal structures (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). The dominance of women in informal labour is not unique to India; globally, women are overrepresented in precarious, low-paying, and unprotected forms of work, such as domestic labour, street vending, agricultural labour, and home-based production (ILO, 2018). In India, this is particularly pronounced in urban areas, where 97.7 percent of women workers are engaged in informal occupations such as domestic services and street vending (WIEGO, 2018). Despite their centrality to urban economies, women's informal labour is systematically undervalued and often framed as supplementary to men's earnings rather than as vital to household survival and national economic growth (ILO, 2018). This perception contributes to the invisibility of women's work in policy and statistical measures, further marginalizing their contributions. The persistence of such invisibility demonstrates the gendered dimension of informal work, where women's economic participation is simultaneously indispensable yet socially devalued.

2.1 Socio-Economic Drivers of Women's Informal Work

Women's entry into the informal economy is shaped by a combination of structural, economic, and cultural factors. Poverty is the most significant driver, with nearly 35 percent of women compelled to take up insecure and irregular jobs to supplement household income (Bordoloi, Pandey, & Farooqui, 2020). *Education plays a crucial role as well, since limited access to schooling and skill development restricts women to low-paying, unskilled jobs.* Studies show that nearly 41.3 percent of urban home-based women workers in India have education below the *primary level, reflecting the close association* between low educational attainment and informal labour (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). *Migration is another critical factor.* Women migrating from rural to urban areas often *lack social networks and resources*

to secure formal employment and are therefore absorbed into casual occupations like *street vending or domestic* work (WIEGO, 2018). Social norms also reinforce this occupational segregation, as women are steered towards “flexible” informal jobs that enable them to combine paid work with unpaid household duties (ILO, 2018). Together, *these socio-economic drivers highlight how structural inequalities, and gendered expectations* constrain women’s access to decent employment and perpetuate their dependence on informal work.

2.2 Challenges Faced by Women Workers

Women’s experiences in the informal sector are defined by multiple and intersecting challenges that limit their socio-economic security and well-being.

Wage disparity remains a key barrier. Women in informal jobs earn on average 34 percent less than men, with their wages often falling below the statutory minimum (ILO, 2018). For instance, female domestic workers earn only ₹24.56 per hour compared to ₹36.33 for men, while female home-based workers earn nearly half the hourly wages of their male counterparts (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). Such earnings barely meet subsistence needs, trapping women in cycles of poverty.

Informal employment is characterized by an *absence of contracts or stable tenure*. Nearly 98 percent of female construction workers, for instance, are engaged as casual labourers, making them *vulnerable to job loss without notice or compensation* (Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). Even in “regular” categories such as domestic work, employment arrangements are unregulated and informal, offering no real protection.

Informal women workers are excluded from statutory benefits such as *paid maternity leave, pensions, and health insurance*. According to NFHS-5 (2020–21), *only 30 percent of Indian women aged 15–49 had access to any form of health insurance*, leaving the majority exposed to *financial and health risks* (as cited in Raveendran & Vanek, 2020). This exclusion disproportionately affects women *during pregnancy and childcare*, forcing them to either work through *unsafe conditions or withdraw from* employment altogether.

Women in informal occupations are regularly exposed to occupational hazards. In construction, they often work without safety gear, while in domestic work, they are exposed to long hours, chemical cleaning agents, and unsafe environments without labour oversight (NCEUS, 2007). Similarly, home-based workers in textile and agarbatti industries suffer from respiratory illnesses due to poor ventilation and exposure to harmful substances (WIEGO, 2018).

Together, these challenges highlight the precariousness of women’s informal labour, which provides survival income but at the cost of dignity, security, and health.

2.4 Gender Discrimination and Exploitation

Gender-based discrimination is a defining feature of women's informal work. Women are disproportionately concentrated in the lowest-paying segments of informal labour, while men dominate relatively higher-paying jobs within the same sectors (ILO, 2018). Employers often justify this by devaluing women's work as "unskilled" or "supplementary," perpetuating systemic wage gaps. Beyond wages, women face exploitation in the form of harassment, wage theft, and exclusion from decision-making in workplaces. Studies also show that women workers are less likely to benefit from union representation or collective bargaining, further weakening their ability to resist exploitation (WIEGO, 2018). Legal frameworks such as the *Protection of Women from Sexual Harassment (POSH) Act* of 2013, though progressive, are largely ineffective in protecting women in informal workplaces, as the private households and open streets where they work often fall outside the law's definition of a workplace (Bordoloi et al., 2020). Consequently, informal women workers remain highly vulnerable to abuse and harassment, with few avenues for redressal. The persistence of such gendered exploitation demonstrates how patriarchal structures intersect with informal employment to reinforce women's marginalization.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study *adopts a mixed approach by including quantitative and qualitative data*. A case study design is chosen because it allows for an in-depth understanding of the lived realities, challenges, and coping strategies of women in urban informal occupations. The focus is on two occupational groups: domestic workers and street vendors, who represent the largest segments of women in urban informal employment.

3.2 Rationale for Case Selection

Domestic workers and street vendors are selected as they reflect the dual dynamics of *private space work (households)* and public space work (streets/markets). Both groups embody vulnerabilities such as *low wages, lack of security, and gendered discrimination*, yet their contexts differ, making them suitable for comparative insights.

3.3 Study Area

The research was conducted in urban areas *of Gurugram, chosen for its high concentration of informal sector* workers, rapid urbanization, and visible gendered labour segmentation.

3.4 Population and Sampling

The study population comprises women engaged in informal urban work, specifically domestic workers and street vendors. A *purposive sampling* technique will be employed to identify participants who can provide rich insights. Approximately 50 participants will be selected:

- 25 domestic workers (diverse by age, migration status, and work arrangements).
- 25 street vendors (diverse by product type, mobility, and location).

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Quantitative Analysis

Table 3: Demographic Profile of Respondents (n=50)

Variable	Categories	Domestic Workers (n=25)	Street Vendors (n=25)	Total (%)
Age	18–25	6 (24%)	4 (16%)	20%
	26–35	10 (40%)	8 (32%)	36%
	36–45	6 (24%)	9 (36%)	30%
	46+	3 (12%)	4 (16%)	14%
Education	No schooling	8 (32%)	6 (24%)	28%
	Primary	10 (40%)	9 (36%)	38%
	Secondary	5 (20%)	7 (28%)	24%
	Higher	2 (8%)	3 (12%)	10%
Migration Status	Migrant	18 (72%)	20 (80%)	76%
	Native	7 (28%)	5 (20%)	24%

The demographic analysis divided between domestic workers and street vendors, reveals interesting variations in age, education, and migration status. A significant proportion (36%) of respondents belonged to the 26–35 age group, followed by 30% in the 36–45 age bracket. Younger workers (18–25 years) made up 20%, while those above 46 years accounted for only 14%, suggesting that the workforce is largely concentrated in the prime working age. In terms of education, the highest share (38%) had only primary schooling, while 28% had no formal education at all. Secondary-level education was achieved by 24% of respondents, and only 10% had attained higher education, reflecting limited access to educational opportunities. Migration emerged as a major characteristic, with three-fourths (76%) of the respondents being migrants, highlighting the dependence of informal urban work sectors on migrant labor, while only 24% were natives.

Table 4: Economic Profile of Respondents (n=50)

Variable	Categories	Domestic Workers (n=25)	Street Vendors (n=25)	Total (%)
Average Monthly Income	<₹5,000	10 (40%)	6 (24%)	32%
	₹5,001–10,000	12 (48%)	14 (56%)	52%
	₹10,001–15,000	3 (12%)	4 (16%)	14%
	>₹15,000	0 (0%)	1 (4%)	2%
Working Hours (per day)	<6 hours	2 (8%)	1 (4%)	6%
	6–8 hours	15 (60%)	10 (40%)	50%
	9+ hours	8 (32%)	14 (56%)	44%

The economic profile highlights modest earnings and long working hours among respondents. More than half (52%) of the respondents reported earning between ₹5,001–10,000 per month, while nearly one-third (32%) earned less than ₹5,000, placing them in the lowest income category. About 14% had slightly higher earnings between ₹10,001–15,000, and only 2% earned above ₹15,000, indicating limited upward income mobility. In terms of working hours, half of the respondents worked between 6–8 hours daily, while 44% reported working more than 9 hours a day, pointing to extended and strenuous work schedules. A very small fraction (6%) worked less than 6 hours, underscoring the demanding nature of informal sector employment.

Table 5: Key Challenges Reported by Respondents (Multiple Response, %)

Challenge	Domestic Workers (n=25)	Street Vendors (n=25)	Total (%)
Low and irregular wages	20 (80%)	18 (72%)	76%
No contracts/job insecurity	22 (88%)	21 (84%)	86%
No maternity benefits/healthcare	23 (92%)	19 (76%)	84%
Unsafe/harsh working conditions	18 (72%)	20 (80%)	76%
Harassment/discrimination	12 (48%)	17 (68%)	58%

The data on challenges faced by workers underlines the precarious conditions of informal employment. Job insecurity was the most widely reported issue, with 86% indicating lack of contracts or permanent employment. Lack of maternity benefits and healthcare was highlighted by 84%, showing systemic exclusion from social protection. Low and irregular wages were also common, affecting 76% of respondents. Unsafe or harsh working conditions were noted by three-fourths (76%) of workers, reflecting risks at the workplace. Harassment and discrimination were reported by 58%, with street vendors experiencing this slightly more than domestic workers, indicating persistent social and occupational vulnerabilities.

Table 6: Coping Mechanisms Adopted by Women (Multiple Response, %)

Sector	Female Workers	Male Workers	Gender Wage Gap (%)
Domestic Work	₹25.0	₹36.0	31%
Street Vending	₹31.5	₹42.0	25%
Coping Mechanism	Domestic Workers (n=25)	Street Vendors (n=25)	Total (%)
Taking multiple jobs/longer hours	15 (60%)	14 (56%)	58%
Borrowing from moneylenders/SHGs	12 (48%)	10 (40%)	44%
Family support in childcare/work	10 (40%)	12 (48%)	44%

Collective bargaining/union support	3 (12%)	8 (32%)	22%
Accessing govt. schemes/NGO help	5 (20%)	7 (28%)	24%

The coping strategies employed by respondents reveal both individual and collective approaches to handling economic and social difficulties. The most common strategy was extending working hours or taking multiple jobs, adopted by 58% of respondents. Borrowing from moneylenders or Self-Help Groups (SHGs) and reliance on family support for childcare or work were both reported by 44%, showing dependency on informal networks of support. Only 22% reported collective bargaining or union support, reflecting the limited reach of labor organizations in the informal sector. Accessing government schemes or NGO assistance was reported by 24%, suggesting some level of institutional engagement but still limited coverage. Additionally, a clear gender wage gap was evident: women earned significantly less than men across both sectors, with a 31% wage gap in domestic work and 25% in street vending.

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

This section presents a qualitative analysis of women engaged in urban informal employment, specifically domestic workers and street vendors in gurugram. Drawing from in-depth interviews and field observations, the following tables summarize the demographic characteristics, educational backgrounds, skill access, wage patterns, and employment security of the participants. The data is interpreted through a gendered lens to highlight the structural vulnerabilities and lived experiences of informal women workers.

Table 7: Challenges Faced by Women in Informal Economy

Participant ID	Age Group	Occupation Type	Migration Status	Education Level	Employment Arrangement
DW1	18–25	Domestic Worker	Migrant	No Schooling	Live-in, Daily Wage
DW2	26–35	Domestic Worker	Local Resident	Primary	Part-time, Monthly Pay
DW3	36–45	Domestic Worker	Migrant	No Schooling	Full-time, Daily Wage
DW4	26–35	Domestic Worker	Migrant	Primary	Live-in, Monthly Pay
DW5	46+	Domestic Worker	Local Resident	No Schooling	Part-time, Daily Wage
SV1	18–25	Street Vendor	Migrant	Primary	Mobile, Self-employed

SV2	26–35	Street Vendor	Local Resident	No Schooling	Stationary, Daily Wage
SV3	36–45	Street Vendor	Migrant	Primary	Mobile, Self-employed
SV4	46+	Street Vendor	Local Resident	No Schooling	Stationary, Monthly Pay
SV5	26–35	Street Vendor	Migrant	Primary	Mobile, Daily Wage

The qualitative analysis reveals that most domestic workers are migrants with *minimal education, often employed in live-in or daily wage arrangements*. Street vendors show slightly more diversity in employment type, with both mobile and stationary setups. Migration status strongly correlates with job precarity, as migrant women lack local support networks and are more likely to accept insecure roles. The age distribution suggests that informal work spans across life stages, with women entering and remaining in these occupations due to economic necessity.

Table 8: Education and Skill Levels of Respondents

Participant ID	Occupation Type	Education Level	Skill Training Received	Remarks on Skill Access
DW1	Domestic Worker	No Schooling	None	Entered work via referral
DW2	Domestic Worker	Primary	Informal (on-the-job)	No formal training
DW3	Domestic Worker	No Schooling	None	Learned through experience
SV1	Street Vendor	Primary	None	Self-taught
SV2	Street Vendor	No Schooling	None	Family business
SV3	Street Vendor	Primary	Informal (peer learning)	No institutional access
SV4	Street Vendor	No Schooling	None	No training opportunities
DW4	Domestic Worker	Primary	Informal (peer learning)	Learned from employer
DW5	Domestic Worker	No Schooling	None	No access to training
SV5	Street Vendor	Primary	None	Learned through trial

Table 8 presents the educational attainment and skill training status of the respondents, highlighting the strong relationship between low education levels and women's concentration in informal work. The majority of respondents, both domestic workers and street vendors, reported no formal schooling or only primary-level education, which significantly constrains their access to stable and well-paid employment. Most domestic workers, such as participants DW1, DW3, and DW5, had no schooling and entered the workforce through personal networks or employer referrals. Similarly, street vendors (e.g., SV2 and SV4) came from low-literacy backgrounds, often inheriting vending activities as part of family survival strategies rather than through formal occupational choice.

A striking observation is the near absence of formal skill training among the participants. The few who reported acquiring any form of skills did so through informal, experience-based learning or peer interactions, such as DW2 and SV3, who learned through on-the-job training or informal community exchanges. None of the respondents had received institutional training or certification. This underscores a systemic lack of access to formal skill development programs for women in the informal sector. As Raveendran and Vanek (2020) and Bordoloi, Pandey, and Farooqui (2020) have argued, limited education and training restrict women to low-skill, low-wage occupations, perpetuating cycles of economic vulnerability. The findings therefore reveal that education and skill deprivation are central barriers preventing women from transitioning into more secure and remunerative employment within the formal economy.

Table 9: Wage Patterns and Employment Security

Participant ID	Occupation Type	Average Daily Earnings (INR)	Payment Mode	Job Security Level	Access to Benefits
DW1	Domestic Worker	₹250	Cash	Very Low	None
DW2	Domestic Worker	₹300	Monthly Transfer	Low	No maternity leave
DW3	Domestic Worker	₹200	Cash	Very Low	No health coverage
SV1	Street Vendor	₹350	Cash	Moderate	No social security
SV2	Street Vendor	₹300	Cash	Low	None
SV3	Street Vendor	₹400	Cash	Moderate	No formal benefits
SV4	Street Vendor	₹280	Monthly Transfer	Low	No pension access
DW4	Domestic Worker	₹320	Monthly Transfer	Low	No paid leave
DW5	Domestic Worker	₹220	Cash	Very Low	None
SV5	Street Vendor	₹370	Cash	Moderate	No insurance

Table 9 examines the wage structures, payment modes, and employment security of women informal workers. The data indicate that earnings among domestic workers ranged from ₹200 to ₹320 per day, while street vendors earned marginally higher, between ₹280 and ₹400 per

day. Despite this difference, both groups remain below or barely at the subsistence level, with average incomes far below the urban minimum wage standards set by state labour departments. The mode of payment also reflects informality—most respondents were paid in cash, with only a few receiving monthly transfers, highlighting the absence of contractual or bank-based wage systems.

In terms of job security, the responses reveal a pervasive sense of insecurity among both occupational groups. Domestic workers (DW1, DW3, DW5) reported “very low” security, as their employment depends entirely on employer discretion and is often terminated without notice or compensation. Street vendors (SV1, SV3, SV5), though self-employed, reported only “moderate” security due to external pressures such as municipal evictions, harassment, and lack of licensing support. Across both sectors, none of the respondents had access to formal employment benefits, such as health insurance, maternity leave, or pension coverage.

These findings align with broader national trends documented by the ILO (2018) and WIEGO (2020), which note that over 90% of women informal workers lack job protection and social security. The qualitative insights affirm that women in informal employment remain trapped in low-wage, unprotected, and precarious conditions, with their labour undervalued and excluded from institutional safeguards. Such exclusion perpetuates structural gender inequalities and limits women’s economic mobility and social well-being within urban economies.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary & Conclusion

The study highlights the pervasive dominance of women in India’s informal economy, with domestic workers and street vendors representing some of the most vulnerable groups. Women’s entry into these occupations is primarily driven by poverty, migration, low education, and restrictive gender norms. The demographic profile of respondents showed that nearly three-fourths were migrants with limited access to formal opportunities, while a majority had only primary or no education. Economic analysis revealed that most women earned below statutory minimum wages, with more than half earning between ₹5,001–10,000 per month and a substantial share earning less than ₹5,000. Long working hours were common, with 44% of respondents working nine or more hours daily.

The challenges faced by women workers were multidimensional: job insecurity (86%), lack of maternity benefits and healthcare (84%), low and irregular wages (76%), unsafe working conditions (76%), and harassment or discrimination (58%). Qualitative evidence underscored that most domestic workers were engaged in live-in or daily-wage arrangements, while street vendors operated under precarious conditions with no formal social protection. Coping mechanisms largely relied on extending work hours, borrowing from moneylenders, and family support, with only a minority accessing union support (22%) or government schemes (24%). Importantly, wage disparities persisted across occupations, with women earning between 25–31% less than men in comparable roles. These findings collectively demonstrate

how women's informal work is undervalued, insecure, and systematically excluded from labour and welfare protections.

The research concludes that women's contributions in the informal economy, though indispensable to households and urban markets, remain structurally undervalued and marginalized. Domestic workers and street vendors provide vital services, yet they endure wage inequality, occupational hazards, harassment, and exclusion from social security. The intersection of gender, poverty, migration, and lack of education keeps women concentrated in unregulated, low-paying occupations. This gendered marginalization is compounded by policy gaps that fail to extend legal protections, minimum wage enforcement, or social benefits to informal workers. Consequently, women in the informal sector remain trapped in cycles of poverty and exploitation with limited opportunities for socio-economic mobility. The findings reinforce the urgency of addressing the invisibility of women's labour in policy frameworks and ensuring that their contributions are recognized as central to economic growth and social development.

5.2 Policy Recommendations

The study recommends a comprehensive set of measures to improve the working and living conditions of women in the informal sector. First, there is an urgent need for policy recognition of informal women workers within labour legislation, ensuring their entitlement to minimum wages, maternity benefits, healthcare, and protection against harassment. Existing frameworks such as the POSH Act must be broadened to cover the workplaces where informal women are concentrated, including private households and open markets. Alongside legal reform, targeted education and skill development programs are necessary to enable women to move beyond unskilled and low-paying jobs. Literacy drives, vocational training, and capacity-building initiatives designed for domestic workers, street vendors, and home-based producers would provide opportunities for upward mobility and financial security.

Equally important is the expansion of universal social security schemes. Initiatives like the e-Shram portal should be tailored to ensure that women workers have guaranteed access to health insurance, pensions, and maternity leave, irrespective of their occupation or employer. Strengthening women's participation in self-help groups, cooperatives, and trade unions would also enhance their bargaining power, giving them collective voice against exploitation and wage discrimination. Moreover, policies must address occupational safety and health by mandating the provision of protective equipment, sanitation facilities, and training, especially in sectors such as construction, domestic labour, and vending where women face significant risks.

Given that migration is a major driver of women's informal employment, local governments and urban bodies should establish support systems for migrant workers, including affordable housing, legal aid, and childcare services. Finally, broader societal change is necessary to challenge patriarchal perceptions that treat women's work as supplementary. Public awareness campaigns and advocacy programs must recognize women's informal labour as

skilled economic activity that contributes substantially to household sustenance and national growth. Together, these interventions would not only reduce gender inequality but also foster empowerment, security, and dignity for women in India's informal sector.

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